

Studies on the Recovery of Zinc, Copper and Lead from 'Sikkim Mineral Concentrates'

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Investigations on the chemical recovery of metals from the 'Sikkim Mineral Concentrates' by conventional roasting or by fluidized-bed sulphate roasting and leaching with dilute acid, showed that about 70%, 56%, and 80% of zinc, copper and lead respectively could be extracted into solution from their respective concentrates. The process of autoclave acid leaching under oxygen pressure, for the zinc concentrate, was examined and it was found that about 80% zinc, in a single leach operation, under optimum conditions, could be extracted into solution.

IN recent years, interest is growing in the processing of sulphidic minerals by the fluidized-bed sulphate roasting technique^{1,2} or by the autoclave acid leaching under oxygen pressure³. A detailed process for the direct leaching of zinc sulphide concentrates with sulphuric acid and oxygen under pressure, with 95-97% zinc recovery was reported⁴. This process, in which roasting is avoided, permits the recovery of sulphur in zinc sulphide as elemental sulphur. Further, the zinc loss in residues caused by ferrite formation in conventional roasting and leaching processes is eliminated. We have carried out investigations at the instance of Sikkim Mining Corporation, Sikkim, which produces annually 20 lakhs worth of sulphidic mineral concentrates for the chemical recovery of zinc, copper and lead from the respective concentrates. The experimental results on (a) conventional roasting and leaching, (b) fluidized-bed roasting and (c) sulphuric acid leaching under oxygen pressure, of the mineral concentrates, are presented here.

Materials

The materials, zinc concentrate, copper concentrate and lead concentrate having the following

TABLE I

Product %	Zinc concentrate*	Copper concentrate	Lead concentrate
Zn	45.5	6.2	5.6
Cu	2.2	21.0	6.0
Pb	3.5	5.8	52.5
Fe	13.2	29.0	—
Total S	33.0	29.75	10.9
Ag Oz/Ton	4	—	—

* Annual production by the Corporation in tons of the zinc concentrate, 1400; copper concentrate, 1000 and lead concentrate, 500.

* N.C.L. Communication No. 1654.

composition (Table 1) were supplied by M/s. The Sikkim Mining Corporation, Sikkim.

Experimental

Conventional roasting of the concentrates was carried out by directly heating the material in a muffle furnace at various temperatures (to convert them to their respective sulphates). The zinc concentrate, for instance, was heated at 750°-800° for 2 hr. and later the calcined mineral was extracted with hot 5% sulphuric acid. Similarly, the copper and lead concentrates were heated at 550°-600° and 750° respectively and the calcined materials were leached with 10% sulphuric acid and saturated brine solution containing 10% sulphuric or hydrochloric acid respectively.

Fluidized-bed sulphate roasting :

The metal roaster, constructed for the purpose, consists of a vertical reactor made out of a mild-steel pipe (12"×2"). The steel-tube was wound externally with nichrome wire and was well insulated. A weighed amount of the dry sample (concentrate) was charged into the unit and dry preheated air was passed with increasing air rates until the solid particles were kept continuously rotated. The sample was then gradually heated. The minimum fluidization velocities for the bed of concentrates were determined experimentally by visual observation of the charge, initially in a Pyrex-glass unit (12"×2") of similar dimensions.

Pressure leaching equipment :

The leaching tests for the concentrates were carried out in a mild-steel lined reactor (9"×6") (fabricated for the purpose) with external heating which could maintain temperature of the reacting mixture within a range of ±5°, and was equipped with stirring arrangement. Commercial oxygen was supplied

through suitable pressure reducing control valves. The experimental procedure followed by conducting leaching tests of the zinc concentrate, was similar to the one described by Forward and Veltman⁴. For instance, the zinc concentrate (-350 mesh), 200 g., was charged to the open reactor as a water slurry. The required amount of sulphuric acid was added with more water and after closing the reactor, oxygen was admitted (to prevent H₂S formation) during the heating period. The reactor was operated continuously for the entire period, with temperature, oxygen pressure and stirring being maintained throughout.

The experiments were carried out at the temperature range 110°-115° (below the melting point of sulphur). Since this temperature range facilitates the formation of finely divided elemental sulphur which can be separated out easily. However, in the experiments the sulphur, on cooling, formed small pellets with unoxidized sulphides.

At the end of the reaction the products namely, solution, residue and pellets were analysed for zinc etc., by the standard methods.⁵

Results and Discussion

Conventional roasting leading to the oxidation of the concentrates to sulphates (Table 2) and subsequent leaching with acid or saturated brine and acid, gave 70%, 56% and 51% recoveries of zinc, copper and lead respectively from their concentrates. The laboratory data obtained by utilizing fluidized-bed sulphate roasting technique showed no particular advantage over the conventional roasting in the recoveries of zinc and copper. However, lead recovery by this technique (fluidized-bed roasting) was improved considerably (80%). Although low-initial roasting temperatures were maintained for the concentrates, to give better solubilities, in view of the appreciable amounts of lead and iron, the recoveries could not be improved. Laist *et al.*⁶, observed that zinc concentrates, with 5% lead or more, in the roasting process, tend to sinter and ball up causing insufficient roasting and low solubility. Large scale tests run by Phelps Dodge Corp. at Douglas, Ariz., have shown that in an ordinary un-muffled multiple-hearth furnace, only about 50% of the copper in a sulphide ore could be converted to the water-soluble form, in the roasting process, because of the lack of precise control of roasting conditions.⁷ However, with the application of the Dorro Fluo Solids process, it is reported² to be now possible to roast copper concentrate or similar

material to obtain a calcine with high percentage of water soluble metal content.⁸

In order to improve further the zinc recovery from the concentrate, a series of experiments have been carried out utilizing the pressure leaching process⁴ which avoids roasting and permits the recovery of sulphur as shown in the following equation.

Optimum conditions for the quantitative reaction of ZnS with H₂SO₄ and O₂ under pressure such as temperature, grind, oxygen partial pressure, time and acid concentration have been ascertained. The results show that when a charge of 200 g. of zinc concentrate with stoichiometric quantity of sulphur acid (for Zn+Pb) was stirred at 110°-115° for 3 hr., under oxygen partial pressure of 40 psi, about 80% zinc could be extracted into the solution. The operating conditions (with O₂ pressure varying)

TABLE 3. EFFECT OF OXYGEN PRESSURE AND THE EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS

Analysis of the products	Oxygen over pressure				
	60 psi	45 psi	40 psi	40 psi	35 psi
<i>Conditions :</i>					
Charge	: Zinc concentrate (200 g)				
Grind	: 100% minus 350 mesh; pulp density : ~14%				
H ₂ SO ₄ addition	: Stoichiometric amount for Zn+Pb				
Temperature	: 110°-115°; Time : 3 hr.				
<i>Solution g/litre</i>					
Zn	19.17	17.79	33.78	32.00	31.01
Fe	16.40	16.00	7.87	16.13	12.80
<i>Pellets %</i>					
Zn	17.49	42.81	29.05	30.35	22.70
S ⁰	25.90	13.18	16.51	26.18	33.70
<i>Residue %</i>					
Zn	1.90	38.00	16.18	—	7.24
Pb	18.40	—	32.91	—	19.08
Fe	1.78	—	9.60	—	15.76
S	3.43	—	11.88	—	11.83
<i>Zinc distribution (based on concentrate), %</i>					
Solution	52	45	82	77	70
Pellets	45	9	10	20	29
Residue	3	46	8	3	1

along with analytical results for typical runs are given in Table 3. Higher oxygen pressures, although

TABLE 2. SULPHUR CONTENT IN THE CALCINED SAMPLES

	Zinc concentrate			Copper concentrate			Lead concentrate
	500°	600°	800°	450°	540°	570°	600°
Total sulphur, %	—	13.9	6.13 5.67	14.3	11.54	15.05	17.20
Sulphide sulphur, %	< 0.40	< 0.5	0.50	—	< 0.50	< 0.50	< 0.50

would accelerate the zinc sulphide oxidation and conversion of Fe^{2+} to Fe^{3+} , were found not favourable for maximum extraction of zinc into the solution. In one experiment (35 psi O_2 partial pressure), some quantity of free sulphur associated (colloidal form) with leach solution, besides the free sulphur present in the pellets, was recovered. In a single test experiment with copper concentrate, the leach solution was found to contain almost the entire zinc present in the concentrate. The zinc extraction, in this instance, was found to be about 96%.

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